

Title: ALEA(s)

BORIS WILMOT

PIERRE COUBEAU

FRANÇOIS GASPARD

1. PROGRAM NOTES

ALEA(s) is an audiovisual collective based in Brussels.

It delivers boiling, improvised performances mixing live drawing, video animation and electronic music.

Focused on the bridges thrown between the three mediums, ALEA(s) performances are often described as immersive, intense and crafted.

ALEA(s) live at B-Seite festival

Licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0). Copyright remains with the author(s).

DOI:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/0000000.0000000>

Music Proceedings of the International Conference on New Interfaces for Musical Expression

NIME'23, May 31–June 2, 2023, Mexico City, Mexico

2. PROJECT DESCRIPTION

ALEA(s) is born from the will to bring back “live playing” to electronic music and digital art performances. Where quite often you see a result without understanding what the artist is really doing, ALEA(s) puts its creative process at the center. Both intellectually and physically since they are performing surrounded by the audience. They play without any safety net, which brings even more tension and emergency to their show.

Mixing brutalism architecture, optical illusions, industrial techno, UK bass amongst other influences, the three mediums (drawing, animation and music) blend together beautifully to create a universe that is dark, textured, organic and raw.

ALEA(s) presenting |x NiŸhi|0 under the dome at the SAT (Montreal)

3. PERFORMANCE NOTES

The trio is working on a table in the middle of the audience. François is playing a dark & textured dancefloor orienteds electronic music, on his modular synths. In front of him, Pierre is busy drawing with charcoal. Boris takes pictures of the drawings, animates them and project the result onto a big screen. From scratch, before the eyes of the audience, they create an intense and immersive AV show.

The backbone of the show is the visual artist's work. Though not as obvious as the musician's or the drawer's roles, he is the one blendings everything and creating a whole experience.

This is done through a homemade software developed on nodal programming software vvvv.

The software is used to capture pictures and play them back sequences, creating animated loops. The artist can then play with the framerate or the length of the loops.

Everything being automatically divided in bars and steps, the animation is always synced to the music.

From there, the goal is to find “happy accidents” in this link between music and visuals (therefore the name “ALEAS” meaning “hazards”).

When you listen to music and watch a video (i.e. when watching a music video), your mind instinctively creates links between what you see and what you hear.

“Ow, the director cut the shot exactly on the snare hit”

“Hey, the movement of this bird is following the crescendo of the guitar”.

Listen to a whole new music on the same images, you'll find other links.

As mentioned, in ALEA(s), the goal is to play with the loops length, speed and offset, to try and find happy accidents : a loop where something happens in the image that matches something happening in the sound.

One of the main points of the process is also to keep the mood of the visuals linked to the mood of the music.

To achieve that, we use the pictures stocked in a “ready line” to play with.

As we play and loop those pictures, the drawer keeps working and we stock the new pictures in a "waiting line".

When the music changes, we switch the “waiting line” to the “ready line” and take all the images from the waiting line to put them in the loops. This allows us to make drastic changes in the visuals.

Media Link(s)

- Video: Presentation <https://youtu.be/81y0pVnWEQE>
- Audio: <http://aleas.bandcamp.com>